

SORSE Workshops: **FAIR4RS**

19 November 2020

Session 2 Breakout Room 3 Notes

Title: How would you want to get credit for making your software FAIR?

Lead: Neil Chue Hong

Participants: all

We'll answer these questions by writing in parallel in the document, then discuss our responses.

When we talk about **credit**, we mean any way of valuing the work that you have put into something. This could be tangible (e.g. a cash bonus) or intangible (e.g. people talk about you)

We're interested in this because it helps FAIR4RS understand how to define its roadmap.

Q1: What are the main (research / software related) activities you receive credit for, and how do you receive that credit? [You can stay anonymous, in which case use another identifier for both your answers]

Name	Activities	Credit received by...
Alejandra	Software developed and published (as a paper) Software developed and published (the software itself) Contribution to open source communities (issues, code/PRs, documentation)	Citations of the publication Software citation Recognition Software reuse
Daniel G	Researcher and software developer	Citations, Github stars, some retweets?
Dominic	Developing a numerical software framework	Citations (not very impressive), getting hired as RSE,
Morane	Articles, reports, contributions in FOSS projects, software conception and design	Salary, mentions, citations, PR acceptance

Fotis	Researcher, publications, lite dev	Citations (sometimes, usually only when in a formal publication, not software as is)
Jean-Noël	Adding new features (or helping integrate contributed features) to the main software developed at research lab, which can then be used by the community	Scientific collaborations with users of these features, funding from grant proposals, papers
Renato	Creation of training materials, contribution to open source projects, Contributing to sustainability vs new features	Publication, Citations, Community Kudos, Recognition, consideration
Anna-Lena	Research and teaching in the field of research software	Student feedback, citations, funding, salary, promotion prospects, retweets, interviews, talk invitations
Mary	Publishing research software/coding materials for teaching, closed and open source library and research software	GitHub stars and forks, retweets, recommendations and praise by colleagues, positive feedback by students, citations/reference in lists/tutorials
Carlos	Maintaining software libraries	Citations of papers where the software is used, users
Leyla	Software developed and published (together with corresponding data and publications)	Citations
Tamora	Collaborate on research software	Co-authorship on published outputs, recognition for group leading to further work
Leyla	Presentations about the software involved in research	Awareness of activities of team/institute

Q2: If you made your software FAIR, what would be the best ways for you to receive credit and why?

Name	I'd like to receive credit by...	This is because....
Fotis	Formal recognition (Institutional, funding agencies, etc)	Get the support to continue making software FAIR :)
Daniel G	Stars (findability) and citations (CV). I would like it counted in my CV. Funding agencies should also take into account this.	Right now software is not credited except for publications, and it is a very rich resource used by the community
Renato	Others finding my software useful and using it, Endorsement, Funding.	Career progression, Recognition as a capable developer,
Morane	Anyone who used my research outputs, specifically software outputs	I'd like positive feedback or any feedback that will improve the software or make me and the subjects I'm interested in to progress
Leyla	Recognition by research community (including funding opportunities, peers, and so)	FAIR implies an effort, I do not want this to be in vain, I want it to be recognized
Carlos	Getting more people using my software (because they are able to find it and use it)	Having people use my tool would show that it has impact / it is not a pointless exercise.
Alejandra	Recognised in promotion activities, citations, reuse, funding, how the software helps in accelerating scientific results	It should be part of the normal software process and recognised as such (most of the time)! :-)
Mary	GitHub badge, consideration in annual review/feedback, software recommended by others because the software is FAIR, credit in grant applications for plan to make software FAIR (i.e. more likely to get funded)	Recognition as a good software engineer who cares, reproduces and passes on best practices, career progression possibly, make grant-funding bodies value and recognise (good) software as valuable
Anna-Lena	Users, software citations, consideration in job evaluation / CV	It takes time and effort, some form of reward/recognition will provide incentive

Dominic	Getting a FAIR “certificate” (a badge, whatever) for my software	It allows funding agencies etc. to make adoption of FAIR mandatory, which is the only way it will work.
Tamora	Some sort of accreditation?	Recognition of effort to make software FAIR
Jean-Noël	Formal recognition (institutional): the effort of making your software FAIR should be seen as a good use of your time as a scientist or RSE	Research software should be FAIR, but needs an incentive

What is the cost of making software FAIR? Does it differ in the short and long term?

What is the appropriate amount of credit to get for making software FAIR?

When should you put in the effort to make software FAIR?

Transcribed comments:

<GitHub badge>:

- Carlos Martinez: One of my colleagues developed this:
<https://github.com/fair-software/howfairis> -- you can get a badge for compliance with FAIR software recommendations from <https://fair-software.eu/>
- Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran: thanks for sharing the link!

<Getting a FAIR “certificate”>:

- Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran: who would be able to give this certificate?
- Daniel Garijo: :D